

The Five Generations of Entity Resolution on Web Data

Konstantinos Nikoletos¹[0000-0003-3465-1197], Ekaterini
Ioannou²[0000-0002-4922-6639], and George Papadakis¹[0000-0002-7298-9431]

¹ University of Athens, Greece {k.nikoletos,gpapadis}@di.uoa.gr

² Tilburg University, Netherlands Ekaterini.Ioannou@uvt.nl

Abstract. Entity Resolution constitutes a core data integration task that has attracted a bulk of works on improving its effectiveness and time efficiency. This tutorial provides a comprehensive overview of the field, distinguishing relevant methods into five main generations. The first one targets Veracity in the context of structured data with a clean schema. The second generation extends its focus to cover Volume, as well, leveraging multi-core or massive parallelization to process large-scale datasets. The third generation addresses the additional challenge of Variety, targeting voluminous, noisy, semi-structured, and highly heterogeneous data from the Semantic Web. The fourth generation also tackles Velocity so as to process data collections of a continuously increasing volume. The latest works, though, belong to the fifth generation, involving pre-trained (large) language models which heavily rely on external knowledge to address all four Vs with high effectiveness.

Keywords: Entity Resolution · Data Integration · LLMs

1 Content & Goals

The process of linking instances describing identical real-world objects and deduplication is known as *Entity Resolution (ER)* [19]. This is a particularly important task for Web Data. Knowledge graphs, ontologies, structured, and semi-structured data are only a few examples of the Web’s data volume and complexity that ER must deal with. To establish links between these entities, numerous techniques have been developed, centered around four key aspects: Veracity, Volume, Variety, and Velocity. In this tutorial, we will explain that ER has evolved through five generations, each with a distinct focus on various aspects.

The **1st ER generation** focused on tackling Veracity, through end-to-end pipelines involving three consecutive steps: *Schema Matching*, *Blocking*, and *Entity Matching*. Each of these steps has a separate role. First, Schema Matching tries to match the relevant attributes across two structured datasets with different schemata [2, 15]. After inter-linking the different schemata, another problem arose. Performing comparisons between every entity and all others would lead to a quadratic time complexity of $O(n^2)$ [4]. Therefore, algorithms and techniques have been designed to mitigate this complexity, aiming to decrease the

number of comparisons and similarity calculations. To address this requirement, a technique known as *Blocking* is introduced. Blocking aims to limit the computational cost by focusing on comparing only the most similar entity profiles. This is achieved by using signatures composed of combinations of parts of values corresponding to the most informative attribute names. Finally, a method for similarity checking between each pair of entities fall in the same block, were added in the ER pipeline. Named *Entity Matching*, this step provides the information if two entities are a match, non-match or uncertain [4]. However, as the needs for ER emerged, more and bigger datasets needed to be evaluated, posing a problem of bringing ER to Big Data challenges.

The **2nd ER generation** tackled Volume and Veracity. It follows the same principles with the 1st generation plus challenges related to Big data. In order to provide ER solutions, with sufficient performance and scalability, several techniques were tested. Firstly, many ER procedures were parallelized and techniques such as Map/Reduce [5] were utilized. Blocks after the Blocking phase could now be handled in parallel, and reduce time complexity drastically [11]. The same parallelization approach can be applied to Entity Matching [3]. However, this raises the issue of Load Balancing between the computational resources [12].

After optimizing the time complexity due to the larger data volumes, highly heterogeneous and noisy data with unclear semantic and contextual information, needed to be processed. For tackling this need, a new generation emerged, the **3rd ER Generation**, tackling Variety, Volume and Veracity. *Variety*, is now the key-point of this era. At this point, schemas should be categorized regardless of their semantics but given the values of each attribute [7]. This method is known as *Schema Clustering*. Schema Clustering was set as the first step of the ER pipeline, and worked in combination with *Blocking* in each of the clusters formed, resulting in increase of the precision without counteracting with recall. In this era, where a schema-agnostic approach is needed, another step, the Block Building, takes all entity profile information and builds blocks without the need of schema alignment and human intervention. In order to optimize the selection of blocks, the next step is to process them. So, a new workflow step was introduced, the Block Processing, which removes insufficient blocks and isolates blocks containing valuable information. As in the previous eras, Entity Matching is again applied to the candidate pairs in each of the blocks generated from the previous steps. A similarity graph is the result of Entity Matching [13, 14, 20], where each node is an entity and each edge the similarity between them. Having this graph, multiple optimization techniques could be added to the ER pipeline, introducing the Entity Clustering step [9].

A new challenge, which will mark the next generation is the speed and cost of performing ER in various datasets, introducing the **4th ER Generation**, tackling Velocity, Variety, Volume and Veracity. Datasets became more dynamic and as the Web was evolving and more apps and systems were deployed, data became bigger and with a more incoming/streaming nature. For this reason, the number of comparisons and/or resources needed should be in many cases restricted. Adding the sense of *budget*, Progressive ER provides practitioners with a pay-as-

gou-go ability, by prioritizing the most valuable comparisons between the data sources. Another approach that emerged in this generation is the Incremental ER [8], that minimizes the cost of updates when a streaming use-case, like a web REST-API, provides a streaming input on the data. Finally, Query-driven ER [1] was defined as a process that systematically resolves entities returned as results to incoming queries over time [10].

After exploring the foundational stages of ER, our tutorial will delve into the latest advancements in methods and algorithms, corresponding to the **5th ER Generation**. We will examine Deep Learning and the impact of Language Models (LMs), particularly pre-trained ones. These models enable the transformation of entity profiles into a vector space, merging textual data with semantic and contextual information extracted from the underlying LMs knowledge base [21]. Finally, we will discuss the current evolution of Language Models, specifically Large LMs (LLMs), which further enhance ER pipelines. LLMs can contribute significantly to both the Block Building and Entity Matching steps. In Block Building, they facilitate the creation of embeddings rich in information, while in Entity Matching, a prompting mechanism to an LLM can yield matching or non-matching predictions.

A hands-on tutorial will also be presented, using pyJedAI [16]. pyJedAI is an open-source Python package implementing most of the pipelines described above. From Blocking to LMs, a developer becomes an architect of the pipelines, as all methods are implemented. Attendees will gain the know-how of tackling in a starting and novice way ER problems, while at the same time will get familiar with a framework that can be used in challenging ER tasks, both in academia and industry as it is available under the Apache License 2.0. Finally, we will present the future of this area and will delve into the challenges and the problems that are still open for work until now, like the auto-configuration of end-to-end ER pipelines [6].

2 Sessions & Target Audience

This tutorial will provide a holistic view over the research status in the area of Entity Resolution, spanning from the first approaches, but emphasizing the latest state-of-the-art research developments. The five ER generations will be presented in chronological time, leading to the following structure:

- (i) **introduction and motivation**, including ER preliminaries, fundamental assumptions, principles, and overview of the generations;
- (ii) **1st generation**, focusing on Veracity, with schema matching, blocking, entity matching, and methods using external Knowledge;
- (iii) **2nd generation** tackling Volume and Veracity, including parallel blocking, parallel entity matching, and load balancing;
- (iv) **3rd generation** tackling Variety, Volume and Veracity with techniques including schema clustering, block building, block processing, entity matching, entity clustering;

(v) **4th generation** tackling Velocity, Variety, Volume and Veracity with progressive and incremental ER, as well as query-driven resolution;

(vi) **5th generation**, leveraging external knowledge with pre-trained LLMs pipelines, and crowdsourcing, LLMs;

(vii) **hands-on session with pyJedAI**; an open-source Python package with which we will build demos from scratch over real data; and lastly

(viii) **challenges and final remarks**, including automatic parameter configuration and future research directions.

The overall duration of this tutorial is 1 hour, with 15 minutes kept for audience questions and brief discussion. There will be an additional hands-on session, lasting 15 minutes, in which we will present applications and demos in ER tasks using pyJedAI.

Target Audience and Learning Outcome. Our tutorial is focusing on providing examples and use-cases on ER for Web data. Novice audience, with a fundamental knowledge on data management and Web engineering, can attend this tutorial. Also, researchers and developers familiar with these ER, will be interested in all the latest advancements about the use of (large) language models, which is the focus of this tutorial. As a result, our tutorial targets a broad audience, including conference attendees with diverse knowledge backgrounds. Additionally, the hands-on session, demonstrating pyJedAI, offers the attendees of this tutorial a starting know-how of addressing an ER problem.

3 Related Material & Presenters

Tutorial Information. A website³ dedicated to our tutorial will be made available few weeks before the tutorial. This will provide the tutorial slides a week prior the presentation date and keep them online afterwards. In addition, the website will provide guidance for using the Entity Resolution toolbox during the hands-on session. The necessary code will be made available under the Apache License 2.0, which allows for both academic and commercial usage.

Related Material. Part of the tutorial is related to a book [18] and a past tutorial [17]. The present tutorial, though, focuses on the fifth generation of ER solutions, emphasizing the use of pre-trained language models as well as of large language models (LLMs) in ER solutions. Note of these very works has been considered in [18, 17].

Presenters. The presenters of this tutorial are active researchers in the area of data integration, data cleaning and entity resolution, for web data. More specifically, *Konstantinos Nikoletos* is a research associate and M.Sc. student at the Department of Informatics of the University of Athens, Greece. *Ekaterini Ioannou* is an Assistant Professor at the Tilburg School of Economics and Management (TiSEM), the Netherlands. *George Papadakis* is a postdoctoral researcher at the Department of Informatics of the University of Athens, Greece.

³ <https://pyjedai.readthedocs.io/en/latest/pages/icwe2024.html>

Acknowledgement. This work was supported by the Horizon Europe project STELAR (Grant No. 101070122).

References

1. Altwaijry, H., et al.: Query: A framework for integrating entity resolution with query processing. PVLDB (2015)
2. Bernstein, P.A., Madhavan, J., Rahm, E.: Generic schema matching, ten years later. PVLDB **4**(11), 695–701 (2011)
3. Böhm, C., et al.: LINDA: distributed web-of-data-scale entity matching. In: CIKM. pp. 2104–2108 (2012)
4. Christen, P.: Data Matching. Springer (2012)
5. Dean, J., Ghemawat, S.: Mapreduce: simplified data processing on large clusters. Commun. ACM **51**(1), 107–113 (2008)
6. Efthymiou, V., et al.: Self-configured Entity Resolution with pyJedAI. In: IEEE Big Data (2023)
7. Golshan, B., Halevy, A., Mihaila, G., Tan, W.: Data integration: After the teenage years. In: PODS. pp. 101–106 (2017)
8. Gruenheid, A., Dong, X.L., Srivastava, D.: Incremental record linkage. PVLDB **7**(9), 697–708 (2014)
9. Hassanzadeh, O., et al.: Framework for evaluating clustering algorithms in duplicate detection. PVLDB **2**(1), 1282–1293 (2009)
10. Ioannou, E., Garofalakis, M.: Query analytics over probabilistic databases with unmerged duplicates. TKDE (2015)
11. Kolb, L., Thor, A., Rahm, E.: Dedoop: Efficient deduplication with hadoop. PVLDB **5**(12), 1878–1881
12. Kolb, L., Thor, A., Rahm, E.: Load balancing for mapreduce-based entity resolution. In: ICDE. pp. 618–629 (2012)
13. Lacoste-Julien, S., et al.: Sigma: simple greedy matching for aligning large knowledge bases. In: KDD. pp. 572–580 (2013)
14. Li, J., et al.: Rimom: A dynamic multistrategy ontology alignment framework. TKDE **21**(8), 1218–1232 (2009)
15. Madhavan, J., Bernstein, P.A., Rahm, E.: Generic schema matching with cupid. In: VLDB. pp. 49–58 (2001)
16. Nikoletos, K., Papadakis, G., Koubarakis, M.: pyJedAI: a lightsaber for Link Discovery. In: ISWC (2022)
17. Papadakis, G., Ioannou, E., Palpanas, T.: Entity resolution: Past, present and yet-to-come. In: EDBT. pp. 647–650 (2020)
18. Papadakis, G., Ioannou, E., Thanos, E., Palpanas, T.: The Four Generations of Entity Resolution. Synthesis Lectures on Data Management, Morgan & Claypool Publishers (2021)
19. Stefanidis, K., Efthymiou, V., Herschel, M., Christophides, V.: Entity resolution in the web of data. In: WWW (2014)
20. Suchanek, F.M., et al.: PARIS: probabilistic alignment of relations, instances, and schema. PVLDB **5**(3), 157–168 (2011)
21. Zeakis, A., Papadakis, G., Skoutas, D., Koubarakis, M.: Pre-trained Embeddings for Entity Resolution: An Experimental Analysis. In: VLDB (2023)